

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe
Grant Agreement
No. 101060075

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

This is the 4th newsletter of the BrightSpace project **WHERE YOU CAN:**

- Find out what BrightSpace is all about
- Read about the latest developments of the project
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is BrightSpace ?

BrightSpace is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to design effective and sustainable strategies to navigate the EU agriculture within a Safe and Just Operating Space.

[Read more »](#) | [Read our project flyer](#)

Dear BrightSpace Community,

As we celebrate BrightSpace's second anniversary this November, it is the perfect moment to reflect on the progress, we have made together in 2024. This project is more than a research endeavour — it is our collective response to one of the most pressing challenges of our time: ensuring EU agriculture thrives within ecological limits while meeting societal needs. None of this would be possible without the diverse and invaluable contributions of our stakeholders, whose input continues to guide our work.

This year has been marked by impactful events and significant milestones. From our 2nd Annual Meeting in Seville in November to the DG Agri Project Clusters Meeting in October and discussions with the Scientific and Policy Advisory Board in September, these gatherings have strengthened our commitment to sustainable strategies for European agriculture. A highlight was our 1st Stakeholder Retreat in Leuven in June, where we presented Safe and Just Space indicators alongside model baseline projections. This productive meeting underscored the importance of inclusivity and dialogue in co-designing solutions to agricultural challenges.

Collaboration remains central to BrightSpace's success. Our partnerships with projects such as LAMASUS, GeneBEcon, and Ration have deepened, while new synergies with Act4CAP27 and STEP-UP exemplify our dedication to leveraging Horizon Europe networks for greater impact. This spirit of cooperation extends to capacity building as well. Through initiatives like the Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN), we are equipping the next generation of experts to model agricultural systems within a safe and just operating space.

Our research dissemination has also flourished this year. Publications in Nature Food and Q Open have advanced the dialogue on sustainable agricultural practices, while events like the OECD Sustainable Productivity Conference, the Pacioli Workshop in Padua, and the EU Climate Dialogues in India allowed us to share insights with global experts and stakeholders. The jointly developed LAMASUS-BrightSpace farm typology, presented to the FADN community, exemplifies our collective progress.

As we look forward to 2025, we are committed to deepening collaboration, expanding partnerships, and delivering impactful solutions. Together, we will continue refining our roadmap to ensure it remains practical, inclusive, and innovative for navigating agriculture's safe and just operating space.

As you explore this newsletter, we hope you gain a deeper understanding of the progress we have made and the exciting prospects on the horizon. Your ongoing support and engagement are the bedrock of our success, and we look forward to achieving even more milestones together in the coming year.

Thank you for being an integral part of the BrightSpace community. Your engagement and support are the foundation of our success.

Wishing you a joyful festive season and a prosperous New Year!

Best regards,

Marc Müller

BrightSpace Project Coordinator, on behalf of the BrightSpace team

Latest news from BrightSpace

BRIGHT SPACE Annual Meeting 5-6 November 2024 Seville, Spain

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BrightSpace Annual Meeting, 5-6 November 2024, Seville, ES

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BRIGHT SPACE Annual Meeting 5-6 November 2024 Seville, Spain

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Read our Press Release in English and in Spanish: BrightSpace Project Annual Meeting

[Read more »](#)

AgEnDes ST&PUP ACT4CAP7 BATModelEEL MATS Trade BRIGHT SPACE LAMASIS TOOLS_CAP

Models and tools supporting agricultural policies
Clustering workshop of Horizon funded projects
EC DG AGRI, Brussels, 22 October 2024

BrightSpace presented & discussed at Cluster meeting

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE SPAB meeting | 16 September 2024

Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB) Meeting | 16 September 2024

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE EC project review meeting | 22 July 2024, online

BrightSpace's 1st Review Meeting 22 July 2024

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE WP12: WP leaders' meeting | 28 June 2024, online

WP12: WP leaders' meeting | 28 June 2024, online

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Capacity Building & Stakeholder Engagement

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1st Stakeholder Retreat

The Safe and Just Operating Space for EU agriculture by 2050

19-20 June 2024
Leuven, Belgium

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1st Stakeholder Retreat
19-20 June 2024, Leuven, BE

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BRIGHT SPACE CAPACITY BUILDING

BrightSpace Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN)

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Capacity Building: BrightSpace Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN)

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Further project Activities

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WP11 Meeting | Online

25
November
2024

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WP11 Meeting, 25 November 2024 | Online

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WP4 meeting | 30 October 2024, online

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WP4 Meeting, 30 October 2024 | Online

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WP12: WP leaders' meeting | 25 October 2024, online

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BrightSpace Project Executive Board Meeting, October 25, 2024

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3rd COMDISS meeting | 28 June 2024, online Project communication, results dissemination and exploitation

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3rd BrightSpace COMDISS Meeting | 28 June 2024, Online

[Read more »](#)

Events of project communication & results dissemination

BrightSpace at Conference:
Thinking outside the box: Food systems with a future

KERN Kompetenzzentrum für Ernährung
Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft, Forsten und Tourismus

Über den Tellerrand
FACHKONGRESS
Ernährungssysteme mit Zukunft

20. & 21. November

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**BrightSpace at conference
"Thinking outside the box:
Food systems with a future"**

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2024 Markets outlook workshop
Tuesday, November 19, 2024 / 14:00 - 17:00 (CET)

Forum for the Future of Agriculture

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**BrightSpace Represented at
FFA 2024 Markets Outlook Workshop**

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OECD **ACT4Cap27** **BRIGHT SPACE**

Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Productivity to Address Food Systems Challenges
Measurement, Data, Drivers and Policies

28 October 2024
PARIS, FRANCE

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**BrightSpace at OECD Conference
28 October, Paris, FR**

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LAMASUS **BRIGHT SPACE** **COOPERATE**

**MEET US AT THE
29TH PACIOLI WORKSHOP**

6-9 October 2024
MONTEGROTTO, ITALY

Pacioli
Building better practices

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**Meet us at 29th Pacioli workshop 6-9
October 2024, Montegrotto, Italy**

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2024 AAEA Annual Meeting

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**BrightSpace presented at the
Agricultural & Applied Economics
Association (AAEA)
2024 Annual Meeting**

29 July 2024
New Orleans, LA
United States

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**BrightSpace presented at the
Agricultural & Applied Economics
Association (AAEA) 2024 Annual Meeting**

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Low Carbon Modelling Workshop
9-10 May 2024
New Delhi, India

**BrightSpace presented
at the EU Climate Dialogues Project**

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**BrightSpace presented at the EU Climate
Dialogues Project - Low Carbon
Modelling Workshop**

[Read more »](#)

BrightSpace reports & Open Access publications

- D1.1 An operational concept for dimensions and indicators of the SJOS
- D3.1 Preliminary report on the impact on Technology, Structural change and Demand side processes
- D4.1 Preliminary report on the impact of agricultural, climate, environmental and trade policies
- D5.1 Concept for model interactions and baseline, and mapping research topics to modelling tools
- D6.1 Report on the list of fundamental model adjustments to better represent the solution space for EU agriculture to stay within the safe space
- D7.1 Report on the functionality and needs to enhance the capacity of the BrightSpace Integrated Modelling Toolbox to better model the EU agricultural just operating space
- D8.1 Report on the provision of a set of promising technologies relevant to Safe and Just Operating Space

For the full list of available reports visit our website's Resources page:
<https://brightspace-project.eu/resources/>

Follow us on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/brightspace-eu-project/>

Upcoming events

- ➔ [EU Agri-Food Days, 10-12 December 2024, Brussels, BE](#)
- ➔ [191th EAAE Seminar, 10-14 February 2025, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, DE](#)
- ➔ [FFA Conference, 1 April 2025, Brussels, BE](#)
- ➔ [2025 AES Conference, 14-16 April 2025, Bordeaux, FR](#)
- ➔ [ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025, 23-27 June 2025 Vienna, AT](#)
- ➔ [2025 EAAE Congress, 26-29 August 2025, Bonn, DE](#)

Networking & Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

WE COOPERATE
Joint session
6 November 2024
Seville, ES

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ACT4CAP27 presented & alignment discussed at BrightSpace Annual Meeting

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PROJECT RESULTS

READ OUR NEW OPEN ACCESS ARTICLE

nature food

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nature > nature food > articles > article

Article | Open access | Published: 23 September 2024

Enhanced agricultural carbon sinks provide benefits for farmers and the climate

Stefan Frank, Andrey Lesca Dresi, Augustynczyk, Petr Havlik, Esther Boero, Tatiana Ermolova, Oliver Eickbo, Fulvio Di Fulvio, Mykole Gusti, James Klotzin, Bekka Lavis, Amanda Palazzo & Michael Wölgast

Nature Food 5, 742-753 (2024) | Cite this article

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1st collaboration meeting | 25 July 2024, online
Stakeholder engagement, project communication, results dissemination and exploitation

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Further highlights from our fellow projects

- ➔ 4th Newsletter out 28/11/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ LAMASUS Annual Meeting, 7-8/11/2024, Seville, ES [Read more »](#)
- ➔ LAMASUS at 63rd ERSA Congress, 26-30/08/2024, Azores, PT [Read more »](#)
- ➔ LAMASUS resources: public deliverables & publications [Read more »](#)

- ➔ 1st Policy Brief issued [Read more »](#)
- ➔ 1st Newsletter out [Read more »](#)
- ➔ ACT4CAP27 1st Stakeholder Meeting 23/10/2024 Brussels, BE [Read more »](#)
- ➔ ACT4CAP27 at OECD Conference, 28/10/2024, Paris, FR [Read more »](#)

- ➔ Science Policy Symposium 23/10/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ Article: Microalgae as feed additives in poultry [Read more »](#)
- ➔ GeneBEcon EC Review Meeting, 21/05/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ GeneBEcon resources: public deliverables & publications [Read more »](#)

- ➔ 4th Stakeholder Forum 02/12/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ Workshop on risk assessment of dsRNA-based pesticides 29/08/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ 4th Newsletter 08/2024 [Read more »](#)
- ➔ 1st Policy Brief 05/2024 [Read more »](#)

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More information will be sent in our next BrightSpace newsletter scheduled for spring 2025.

Thank you for signing up to the [BrightSpace newsletters](#).

Further information can be found on the BrightSpace project homepage:

www.brightspace-project.eu | www.brightspace-horizon.eu

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